

Comparison between PI and PR Current Controllers in Grid Connected PV Inverters

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Abstract : This paper presents a comparison between Proportional Integral (PI) and Proportional Resonant (PR) current controllers used in Grid Connected Photovoltaic (PV) Inverters. Both simulation and experimental results will be presented. A 3kW Grid-Connected PV Inverter was designed and constructed for this research.

Keywords : Inverters, Proportional-Integral Controller, Proportional-Resonant Controller, Photovoltaic.

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